

MONITORING OF MICROBIOLOGICAL CONDITION OF IRRIGATED SOILS IN TASHKENT REGION

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Abstract. As a result of monitoring the microbiological condition of the soils in the cotton fields of the "Chinoz Turabek Imkon Plus" farm located in Chinoz district, Tashkent region, it was found that the quantity of the main physiological groups of microorganisms in these soils are low. It was observed that in the 0-10 cm layer of the soil, the amount of ammonifying bacteria, Azotobacteria, oligonitrophile and cellulose-decomposing microorganisms was one order of magnitude lower than in the 20-30 cm layer, while the amount of butyric acid bacteria, on the contrary, was one order of magnitude higher. Among the ammonifying bacteria, *Bacillus mycoides*, *B.atrophaeus*, *B.megaterium*, *Pseudomonas spp.*, free-living nitrogen-fixing bacteria *Azotobacter spp.*, *Clostridium spp.* and fungi *Aspergillus spp.*, *Mucor spp.*, *Fusarium spp.*, *Penicillium spp.*, *Trichoderma spp.* were detected.

Keywords: microbiological monitoring, ammonifying bacteria, phosphorus-mobilizing micromycetes, oligonitrophilic microorganisms, actinomycetes, fungus, humus-degrading bacteria, cellulose-degrading microorganisms.

Introduction

Soil microbial diversity, developed through evolution, plays a key role in crop sustainability by enriching soils and reducing stresses. Under the influence of agrochemicals and soil disturbances, agroecosystems are degraded, reducing farming efficiency exacerbated by climate change. The study and utilization of microbiota of phyllosphere, endosphere, spermosphere, spermosphere, rhizosphere and nerisosphere can be a strategy for sustainable agriculture. Microbiota improves nutrient availability, water uptake and plant resistance to biotic and abiotic stresses. The introduction of beneficial microbes or consortia promotes plant growth, increases resistance to drought, salinity, toxins, diseases and pests, strengthening agroecosystems [1]. Plants in the natural environment interact with a variety of soil microorganisms that improve their mineral nutrition. Recently, the full spectrum of plant microbes and their potential to replace synthetic agro-agro-agents has been actively explored. Plants shape the microbiome through root exudates and bacteria adapt to the rhizosphere. However, the mechanisms of these interactions remain poorly understood [2]. Microbiome also helps in defense against pathogens through niche competition, production of antimicrobial agents, easy availability of nutrients, release of secondary metabolites and induction of systemic resistance which activates the plant defense system against initial pathogen attack [3, 4].

Soil microorganisms are an important component of both natural and managed ecosystems. Despite the challenges of survival in soil, a gram of soil can contain thousands of different microbial taxa, including viruses and representatives of all three domains of life. Recent advances in marker genes, genomic and metagenomic analysis have greatly improved our ability to characterize the soil microbiome and identify factors that influence microbial community formation in space and time. This approach will help utilize genomic information to predict the

functional properties of individual taxa. The field is now poised to explore how the soil microbiome can be manipulated and managed to increase fertility, improve agricultural production, and advance our understanding of the response of terrestrial ecosystems to environmental change [5].

Soil microorganisms play a crucial role in nutrient cycling, maintenance of soil fertility and soil carbon sequestration, and the soil microbiome has both direct and indirect effects on plant and animal health in terrestrial ecosystems [6]. The composition of soil microflora is very diverse: nitrogen-fixing and ammonifying bacteria, micromycetes, actinomycetes, soil algae, bacteria involved in the cycling of trace elements such as iron, phosphorus, sulfur, etc. [7].

Survival and growth of microorganisms in soil environments is often severely limited. There are constant abiotic stressors such as low water availability, limited organic carbon substrates and acidic conditions, high competition with other soil taxa (e.g., widespread distribution of antibiotic-producing and antibiotic-resistant bacteria), frequent disturbances (drying and rewetting, predation by earthworms and other fauna, and freezing and thawing), and uneven distribution of resources in space and time [8-10]. Apart from soil pH, the most important factors that have a marked effect on soil bacterial community structure are likely to be nitrogen availability [11], soil organic carbon content [12], temperature, and redox status [13].

Considering the above, understanding the importance of soil microflora, improving it in terms of quantity and quality, and scientifically approaching this process are considered an important and urgent issue.

Regular monitoring of soil microbiological condition allows timely detection of negative changes in soil ecosystems caused by salinization, degradation of organic matter and unbalanced application of fertilizers.

From this perspective, the aims of our research are to monitor and study the microbiological condition of irrigated soils in Tashkent region.

Materials and methods

The object of the study was soil samples taken from different soil layers of cotton fields of the farm "Chinoz Turabek Imkon Plus" of Chinaz district, Tashkent region. Soil samples for microbiological analysis were collected in spring 2024. Samples were taken according to the envelope principle with observance of sterility from the depth of 0-10, 10-20 and 20-30 cm according to the method. Seeding of microorganisms of the studied groups was carried out by depth method from different dilutions of soil suspension on the following nutrient media: Chapek's medium for the growth of fungus, meat-peptone agar (MPA) for ammonifying bacteria, Pikovskaya's medium for phosphorus-mobilizing microorganisms, Eshbi's medium for oligonitrophilic microorganisms, starch-ammonia agar (SAA) for actinomycetes and microorganisms using mineral forms of nitrogen, Getchenson's medium for cellulose-degrading microorganisms, soil agar medium for humus-degrading microorganisms. Seeds were placed in a thermostat at +28 °C. The counting of fungus was made on the 7th day from the moment of sowing, ammonificators - on the 3rd day, oligonitrophils and actinomycetes - on the 10th day, humus and cellulose-degrading microorganisms - on the 12th day. The number of microorganisms was calculated in colony-forming units (CFU) per gram of absolutely dry soil. A suspension was prepared from the soil samples taken for microbiological analysis. For this, 10 grams of the soil sample was taken, mixed with 90 ml of sterile water and shaken in a shaker for 30 minutes. This process was continued serially, diluted to 1:1000000 and repeated. 1 ml of the liquid in the test

tube was inoculated into specific solid selective nutrient media in a Petri dish, on a "dilution" basis in triplicate, and tested.

The amount of bacteria, yeasts, actinomycetes and fungi per 1 gram of dry soil was calculated using the following formula;

$$a = \frac{b \times c \times g}{d}$$

in this; a - the number of cells in 1 g of dry soil, b - the average number of colonies in a Petri dish, c - the separation used for sowing, g - the number of drops in 1 ml of suspension, d - the weight of dry soil taken for analysis[14].

Starch-ammonia nutrient medium (pH 7.2) g/l: starch - 10; $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ - 1.0; K_2HPO_4 - 1.0; $\text{MgSO}_4 \times 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ - 1.0; NaCl - 1.0; CaCO_3 - 3.0; agar-agar - 20. Soil-agar medium (pH 7.2) g/l: soil extract (1 kg soil+1 L H_2O) - 40; agar-agar - 20. Chapek's medium (pH 4.5) g/l: sucrose - 30; NaNO_3 - 2.0; KH_2PO_4 - 1.0; $\text{MgSO}_4 \times 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ - 0.5; $\text{FeSO}_4 \times 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ - traces; agar-agar - 20. Aerobic cellulose-degrading microorganisms were identified in Hutchinson-Clayton liquid nutrient medium. Composition of Hutchinson-Clayton liquid nutrient medium, g/L (tap water): K_2HPO_4 - 1.0; $\text{MgSO}_4 \times 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ - 0.3; CaCl_2 - 0.1; NaCl - 0.1; FeCl_3 - 0.01; NaNO_3 - 2.5; pH 7.2-7.3. The number of cellulose-degrading anaerobic microorganisms was determined in Omelyansky's liquid nutrient medium. Filter paper was placed on the bottom of test tubes in strips. Composition of Omelyansky's liquid nutrient medium, g/l: K_2HPO_4 - 1.0; $\text{MgSO}_4 \times 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ - 1.0; NaCl - 1.0; $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ - 2.0; CaCO_3 - 2.0. Bacteria producing butyric acid were detected in liquid Vinogradsky's nutrient medium. Composition of liquid nutrient medium of Vinogradsky, g/l: glucose - 20; K_2HPO_4 - 1.0; $\text{MgSO}_4 \times 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ - 1.0; NaCl - 1.0; $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ - 2.0; CaCO_3 - 20.0. The incubation period is 20-25 days at a temperature of +28-30° C. The results are processed according to McCready's table [14].

Soil agrochemical parameters are as follows: pH - 7.69; total salt content - 0.077%; electrical conductivity - 0.18 EC/m; density - 0.083%, humus - 0.82%; total nitrogen content - 0.052%; total phosphorus content - 0.18%; total potassium content - 0.61%; Carbon C - 0.47%, mobile phosphorus - 14.5 mg/kg and mobile potassium - 171.8 mg/kg.

Statistical processing of experimental data was carried out by standard methods of calculating errors, mean, confidence intervals, and standard deviations. All calculations and mathematical analyses were performed using Microsoft Excel 2007.

Results and Discussions

Soil microorganisms constitute a significant part of global biodiversity [15] and contribute to key soil functions such as nutrient cycling [16]. Therefore, their abundance, diversity and functions are integral [17]. An aggregate of microorganisms capable of performing the same general physiological function in the chain of substance transformation is commonly referred to as a physiological group in microbiology. Examples are physiological groups of microorganisms involved in nitrogen transformations (nitrifiers, ammonifiers, denitrifiers, nitrogen fixers). Ammonification is one of the most important stages of the nitrogen cycle in nature, and this process occurs under aerobic and anaerobic conditions. Ammonifying bacteria break down proteinaceous organic matter to ammonium ions.

Previously, microbiological monitoring of soils of 12 cotton fields in the Jizzakh region was carried out. As a result of the monitoring, it was revealed that the number of ammonifying,

phosphorus-mobilizing and oligonitrophilic bacteria in all samples was 1-2 orders of magnitude lower than the norm, and actinomycetes - 2-3 orders of magnitude lower than the norm. Free-living nitrogen-fixing bacteria were not detected. This indicates low absorption of these elements and reduced activity of biological processes. Reduced numbers or complete absence of microorganisms of the main physiological group leads to a decrease in the formation of humus in the soil and the coefficient of absorption of mineral fertilizers (nitrogen, phosphorus, potassium), which prevents the full absorption of biogenic elements by plants [18].

In the course of microbiological monitoring of soil of cotton field of farm "Chinoz Turabek Imkon Plus" of Chinaz district of Tashkent region the total number and composition of microorganisms of different physiological groups in 0-10, 10-20 and 20-30 cm layers of soil was determined.

As a result of microbiological monitoring, it was found that in the studied soils in spring the number of ammonifying bacteria per gram of soil was an order of magnitude higher in the 0-10 and 20-30 cm soil layers than in the 10-20 cm soil layer and averaged $5.1-3.0 \times 10^5$ CFU/g, respectively. Their number in the 10-20 cm soil layer was 6.7×10^4 CFU/g. In the 10-20 cm soil layer, the species *Bacillus mycoides*, a bacterial species belonging to the *Bacillus* genus, was found, and their average amount in 1 gram of soil was 1.5×10^4 CFU/g (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Total number and appearance of ammonifying bacteria in MPA nutrient medium

In soil, bacilli participate in many processes related to the decomposition of various organic substrates (proteins, starch and other polysaccharides), constituting a group of hydrolytics.

When analyzing the microbial community of saline soils of the cotton fields of the Nishan district of Kashkadarya region, it was observed that the number of microorganisms of the main physiological groups was lower, and some groups were completely absent. In particular, it was found that ammonifying bacteria were found in the 20-30 cm layer of soil by an order of magnitude more (1.5×10^5 CFU/g) than in the upper layers, while oligonitrophilic microorganisms were found in this layer less often (4.5×10^3 CFU/g) [19].

Soil contains many microorganisms, among which phosphate-solubilizing microorganisms are present in huge numbers. Microorganisms play an important role in inorganic phosphorus cycling [20, 21]. Phosphate-solubilizing microorganisms account for 50% of the microbial population present in soil [22].

In the soil samples we studied, phosphorus-mobilizing bacteria were not found, but fungi were observed growing in the 10-20 and 20-30 cm soil layers. These fungi belonged to the genus *Mucor* and were found to mobilize $\text{Ca}_3(\text{PO}_4)_2$ from Pikovskaya's medium, changing the color of the medium (Fig. 2).

The number of oligonitrophilic microorganisms in the 0-10 and 10-20 cm soil layers was one order of magnitude higher than in the 20-30 cm soil layer, averaging $2.0-1.5 \times 10^5$ CFU/g per

gram of soil, and 8.2×10^4 CFU/g in the 20-30 cm layer. In this nutrient medium, the growth of fungal species belonging to the genus *Mucor* was also observed in the 10-20 cm layer of soil.

Figure 2. Growth of phosphorus-mobilizing fungi by changing the color of Pikovskaya's medium

The results of determining the amount of micromycetes in the studied soil samples showed that their low abundance was recorded in the 20-30 cm layer and averaged 1.5×10^2 CFU/g of spores, while in the 0-10 and 10-20 cm soil layers, the average was $7.5-2.2 \times 10^3$ CFU/g of spores, respectively. Species belonging to the genus *Aspergillus* were found in the 0-10 cm layer and accounted for 1.5×10^2 CFU/g of spores, respectively. A fungal species belonging to the genus *Mucor* was found in the 10-20 cm layer of soil and was observed to grow covering the surface of the nutrient medium in the Petri dish (Fig. 3).

Figure 3. Total number and appearance of fungus in Chapeka medium
a - diluted 100 times; b – diluted 1000 times:

The natural habitat of actinomycetes is soil; their main ecological role is decomposition of organic matter on the surface and in the soil column. Actinomycetes form hydrolytic enzymes and participate in the decomposition of cellulose, chitin, lignin, humus-like compounds in soil.

The amount of actinomycetes in the SAA medium was uniform in all analyzed soil layers, averaging $6-3-3.7 \times 10^3$ CFU/g per gram of soil. Among actinomycetes, species belonging to the genus *Streptomyces* were observed. White, gray, pink and yellow actinomycetes were distinguished by their color. Along with actinomycetes, bacteria and fungi were also observed to grow in the SAA medium, and bacteria were found in all soil layers in the same order ($2.6-2.1-1.1 \times 10^5$ CFU/g). Microscopic fungi were also found in the same order, averaging $1.2-1.9-3 \times 10^3$ CFU/g of spores, and species belonging to the genera *Aspergillus* and *Mucor* were found (Fig. 4).

Cellulose is the most widespread organic compound in nature, and its synthesis ranks first in terms of scale. Cellulose is mainly created by higher plants, which consist of 40-70% cellulose. Cellulose decomposition is hardly the largest natural destructive process in terms of scale. It is in this part of the carbon cycle that soil microorganisms act as geochemical agents that ensure the return of carbon to the atmosphere in the form of CO_2 . This is the main, but not the only significance of microbial decomposition of cellulose. This process is associated with the formation of humus substances in the soil and the formation of soil structure [7].

Figure 4. Total number and appearance of bacteria, actinomycetes and fungus in SAA medium (a - diluted up to 100 times; b – diluted up to 1000 times)

In this regard, cellulose-degrading microorganisms were also studied in the studied soils. Cellulose-degrading bacteria, actinomycetes, and fungi were found to grow on Hutchenson agar medium. The amount of cellulose-degrading bacteria grown on this medium was found to be the same in the 0-10, 10-20, and 20-30 cm layers of soil ($9\text{-}3\text{-}5 \times 10^3$ CFU/g), and the amount of fungi was found to be higher in the 0-10 cm layer of soil, i.e., an average of 1.8×10^4 CFU/g spores per gram of soil. In the lower 10-20 and 20-30 cm layers of soil, $8\text{-}5 \times 10^3$ CFU/g of spores were observed, and actinomycetes ($9\text{-}6 \times 10^2$ CFU/g) were also observed in these soil layers. Fungi belonging to the genera *Aspergillus*, *Mucor*, *Fusarium* and *Penicillium* were found on Hutchenson agar medium (Fig. 5).

Figure 5. Total number and appearance of microorganisms in Hutchenson agar medium

Humus-decomposing microorganisms were found in all soil layers in the same order, and their total amount was on average 10^5 CFU/g of soil. The growth of bacteria, fungi and actinomycetes was observed in the soil agar medium, and the total amount of bacteria was on average $3.4\text{-}3.6\text{-}2.4 \times 10^5$ CFU/g in all analyzed soil layers, while fungi in the 0-10 and 10-20 cm layers were on average $1.2\text{-}1.3 \times 10^4$ CFU/g of spores, and actinomycetes in the $6\text{-}9 \times 10^3$ CFU/g. Species belonging to the genera *Azotobacter* and *Clostridium* were found in the soil agar medium. *Clostridium* spp. were found in the 0-10, 10-20 and 20-30 cm soil layers. Species averaged $6\text{-}4.2\text{-}1.5 \times 10^2$ CFU/g, while in the 0-10 and 10-20 cm soil layers, *Azotobacter* spp. species averaged $4.5\text{-}6.0 \times 10^2$ CFU/g. In the 20-30 cm soil layer, *Azotobacter* spp. species were observed to be one order of magnitude less abundant (3×10^1 CFU/g) than in the upper layers (Fig. 6).

The number of the main physiological groups of soil microorganisms grown on different media were converted to decimal logarithms and the mean values were calculated for each sample and the results are presented in Figure 7.

In the Hutchinson-Clayton liquid medium, cellulose-decomposing aerobic microorganisms were found in the same order in the 0-10 and 20-30 cm layers of the soil, and their number was on average $3.0-1.5 \times 10^4$ CFU per 1 gram of soil, while in the 10-20 cm soil layer, their number was one order of magnitude lower (9.5×10^3 CFU/g).

Figure 6. Total number and appearance of species belonging to the genera *Azotobacter* and *Clostridium* in Soil-agar medium

Anaerobic decomposition of cellulose produces many organic acids (acetic, succinic, lactic, butyric, formic acids), ethyl alcohol, carbon dioxide and hydrogen.

It was found that the number of anaerobic microorganisms that decompose cellulose in the Omelyansky liquid medium was uniform in all soil layers, averaging $1.5-2.5-4.5 \times 10^2$ CFU/g of soil.

While the average concentration of butyric acid bacteria in the 0-10 and 10-20 cm soil layers was $1.5-4.5 \times 10^4$ CFU/g, in the lower 20-30 cm layer their number was two orders of magnitude higher, averaging 1.4×10^6 CFU/g.

Figure 7. Average number of main physiological groups of microorganisms in cotton fields of Chinaz district of Tashkent region, lg CFU/g of soil

Conclusion

Thus, according to the results of monitoring the microbiological condition of soils of cotton fields of the farm "Chinoz Turabek Imkon Plus" of Chinaz district of Tashkent region, it was found that the number of microorganisms of the main physiological group in these soils was below the norm, and phosphorus-mobilizing bacteria were completely absent. It was found that in the 0-10 cm soil layer the number of ammonifying bacteria, nitrogen-producing bacteria, oligonitrophilic and cellulose-degrading microorganisms was one order of magnitude lower than in the 20-30 cm layer, and the number of fatty acid-producing bacteria was two orders of magnitude higher. In the 0-10 cm soil layer, the total number of ammonifying bacteria, oligonitrophiles and humus-degrading microorganisms averaged $5.1-2.0-3.4 \times 10^5$ CFU/g, fungus and actinomycetes $7.5-6 \times 10^3$ CFU/g, cellulose-degrading microorganisms 1.5×10^5 CFU/g, cellulose-decomposing microorganisms are 2.7×10^4 CFU/g, *Clostridium* spp. and *Azotobacter* spp. were $6-4.5 \times 10^2$ CFU,

respectively. Ammonifying bacteria *Bacillus mycoides*, *B. atrophaeus*, *B. megaterium*, *Pseudomonas* spp., free-living nitrogen-fixing bacteria *Azotobacter* spp., *Clostridium* spp. and fungi *Aspergillus* spp., *Mucor* spp., *Fusarium* spp., *Penicillium* spp., *Trichoderma* spp. were detected. In order to normalize and improve the microflora of these soils, it is recommended to use organic fertilizers and microbial preparations based on indigenous microorganisms.

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